

International Conference on Microbial Biotechnology and Future Bio-industries

Paris, France, June 2020

One-pot synthesis of novel indoline-phthalazin hybrids Under solvent-free conditions As a green and convenient protocol

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Indoline-phthalazin hybrids under solvent-free conditions as a green and convenient protocols have been synthesized using Friedländer heteroannulation reaction from some acids and derivatives catalyzed by nano-zinc oxide. Using eco-friendly Nano-catalyst led to mild reaction conditions and increasing in converted yields. Heterogeneous media makes easy work-up and high isolated yields. The use of ethanol as a green and environmental solvent is the other advantage of this method. Our studies were shown that steric factors have been found to be important in the formation of the desired product. Good and excellent yield (50-97%) was obtained for corresponding compounds. Characterization of products was performed by FT-IR, ¹H- and ¹³C-Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopies, and elemental analysis. The retention factor, R_f, and melting point for these desired products were determined.